

IDENTIFICATION OF DEGRADANTS OF THERMAL STRESS STUDIES OF DAPAGLIFLOZIN TABLETS BY HPLC-PDA AND LC-MS INSTRUMENTAL TECHNIQUES

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ABSTRACT

Objective of the manuscript is to identify the degradants observed in the thermal degradation sample of Dapagliflozin tablets by using LC-MS and HPLC-PDA techniques. Thermal degradation sample was injected in HPLC-PDA and LC-MS instruments. Mass of the degradants were detected by LC-MS technique, which were assigned to the probable structures correlating with the impurities mentioned in the USP monographs of Dapagliflozin tablets. The assigned probable structures for the degradants were confirmed by procuring and confirming by injecting in HPLC-PDA detector and LC-MS instruments.

KEYWORDS: Dapagliflozin, Impurities, Degradants, Structures, HPLC-PDA, LC-MS.

1. INTRODUCTION

Dapagliflozin propanediol mono hydrate (**Figure 1**) is an anti-diabetic drug that prevents glucose reabsorption in the kidney. IUPAC name of Dapagliflozin propanediol monohydrate is (2*S*,3*R*,4*R*,5*S*,6*R*)-2-[4-Chloro-3-(4-ethoxybenzyl)phenyl]phenyl]-6-(hydroxymethyl)tetrahydro-2*H*-pyran-3,4,5-triol,(2*S*)-1,2-propanediol, monohydrate, having the molecular formula of $C_{21}H_{25}ClO_6 \cdot C_3H_8O_2 \cdot H_2O$ and molecular weight of 502.98 g/mol. Dapagliflozin acts by inhibiting selectively human Sodium-Glucose Co-Transporter (SGLT2), the major transporter responsible for glucose reabsorption. Literature survey indicates that Dapagliflozin has been estimated quantitatively from bulk API and pharmaceutical dosage forms.^[1-2] Related substances methods by HPLC are reported for bulk API and very few in tablet dosage forms.^[3-7] Recently this research group published in this journal an article on development and verification of a simple, sensitive, specific, accurate, precise and linear RP-HPLC method for the quantification of Dapagliflozin related substances in Dapagliflozin tablets.^[8] Here, this article talks about the identification of the structures of the degradants generated in the thermal degradation study of Dapagliflozin tablets using HPLC-PDA and LC-MS instrumental techniques.

Figure 1: Structure of Dapagliflozin Propanediol monohydrate.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Chemicals and reagents

An analytically pure sample of Dapagliflozin propanediol monohydrate and their related impurities with purities greater than 90% were used for the study, and the tablet formulation was prepared in our Formulation R&D laboratory, with a label claim of 10mg of Dapagliflozin. Acetonitrile (HPLC grade of Standard make), Methanol (HPLC grade of Standard make), orthophosphoric acid (OPA) (Finar HPLC grade) and water (Milli Q) were used for the analysis.

2.2 Instruments

HPLC analysis was performed on Agilent and Waters makes HPLC's having UV/PDA detector capable of setting detection wavelength of 225 nm. A reverse phase Agilent

Poroshell 120 EC- C18 column, (250 X 4.6 mm; 2.7 μ m), part number 690975-902 is finalized for the method. The HPLC system was controlled with “EMPOWER” software. LCMS instrument used AB Sciex /QTRAP 4500. An electronic analytical weighing balance (0.1mg sensitivity, Sartorius make, ME5 model), Sonicator (Hwashin Make, Power sonic 420 model), Water purification system (Merck make, Milli-Q IQ 7000 model) and Centrifuge (Eppendorf make, 5810 model) were used for the analysis.

2.3 HPLC Chromatographic conditions^[8]

The developed method uses a reverse phase Agilent poroshell 120 EC- C18 column, (250 X 4.6 mm; 2.7 μ m), part number 690975-902, mobile phase-A consisting of 0.05% OPA: Methanol in the proportion of 90:10 v/v, mobile phase-B consisting of Water : Acetonitrile in the proportion of 30:70 v/v, flow rate of 0.9 ml/min, injection volume of 5 μ L, detection wavelength of 225 nm using a UV/PDA detector, setting column temperature and sample compartment temperature of 40°C and 5°C respectively and run time as 35 minutes for gradient program.

Time	Mobile phase A	Mobile phase B
0.0	50	50
1.0	50	50
10.0	35	65
20.0	10	90
25.0	10	90
25.10	50	50
35.0	50	50

2.4 Reagents solution preparation

Mobile phase Buffer (0.05%-OPA) Preparation

Mixed 0.5 ml of Ortho-phosphoric acid in 1000 ml of water and degassed in a sonicator for 10 minutes.

Mobile phase A

Mixed 0.05% Ortho-phosphoric acid buffer and methanol in the ratio of 90:10 v/v respectively followed by degassing in a sonicator for 10 minutes.

Mobile phase B

Mixed water and acetonitrile in the ratio of 30:70 v/v respectively followed by degassing in a sonicator for 10 minutes.

Diluent Preparation

The diluent solution was prepared by mixing water and Acetonitrile in the proportion of 20:80 v/v respectively followed by degassing in a sonicator for 10 minutes.

Preparation of stock and diluted standard solution

Weigh accurately about 50 mg of Dapagliflozin propanediol standard and transfer into a clean and dried 25 ml volumetric flask. Later add 15 mL of the diluent, sonicate to dissolve. Dilute to volume with the diluent and mix well to get a standard stock concentration of about 2000 μ g/mL.

Further diluted 4 ml of above standard stock solution into a clean and dried 200 ml of volumetric flask, make up to the mark with diluent and mix well mix well to get a working standard concentration of about 40 μ g/mL.

Further diluted 6 ml of above standard stock solution (concentration of about 40 μ g/mL) into a clean and dried 200 ml of volumetric flask, make up to the mark with diluent and mix well to get a diluted standard concentration of about 1 μ g/mL, inject into HPLC.

Preparation of stock and sample solution

Drop ten doses of tablets into a clean and dry 200 mL volumetric flask. Add 40 mL of the water and then sonicate for 10 minutes (maintain the temperature of water in sonicator between 20-25°C) with intermittent shaking. Later add 100 ml of acetonitrile, sonicate for 20 minutes (maintain temperature of water in sonicator at 25°C) with intermittent shaking and make up to the mark with acetonitrile and mix well to get a sample concentration of about 500 μ g/mL. Centrifuge a portion of the sample solution at 3000 rpm for 10 minutes. Inject the supernatant into HPLC.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Identification by LC-MS and HPLC-PDA

Dapagliflozin tablets were subjected to the thermal stress at 105°C for 8 hours and later injected into HPLC-PDA detector and LC-MS instruments. Thermal stress sample gave 2 unknown impurities/degradants, whose M+1 fragment ions have m/z values of 407 and 423 (**Figure 2**). To understand the probable structures corresponding to these masses of the degradants, retrieved the structures of the known impurities mentioned in the USP monographs of Dapagliflozin and Dapagliflozin tablets, summarized in **Table 1**.^[9-10]

Table 1: Summary of the Dapagliflozin impurities reported in USP monographs.^[8-9]

Reference	Impurity Name	Structures, IUPAC name	Molecular weight
Dapagliflozin tablets USP monograph	Hydroxy Dapagliflozin	<p>(2<i>S</i>,3<i>R</i>,4<i>R</i>,5<i>S</i>,6<i>R</i>)-2-{4-Chloro-3-[(4-ethoxyphenyl) (hydroxy) methyl] phenyl}-6-(hydroxymethyl)tetrahydro-2<i>H</i>-pyran-3,4,5-triol</p>	C ₂₁ H ₂₅ ClO ₇ ; 424.9
	Desethyl Dapagliflozin	<p>(2<i>S</i>,3<i>R</i>,4<i>R</i>,5<i>S</i>,6<i>R</i>)-2-[4-Chloro-3-(4-hydroxybenzyl)phenyl]-6-(hydroxymethyl)tetrahydro-2<i>H</i>-pyran-3,4,5-triol</p>	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ ClO ₆ ; 380.8
	Oxo Dapagliflozin	<p>2-Chloro-5-[(2<i>S</i>,3<i>R</i>,4<i>R</i>,5<i>S</i>,6<i>R</i>)-3,4,5-trihydroxy-6-(hydroxymethyl)tetrahydro-2<i>H</i>-pyran-2-yl]phenyl}(4-ethoxyphenyl) methanone</p>	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ ClO ₇ ; 422.9
	Dapagliflozin Related compound A	<p>((2<i>S</i>,3<i>R</i>,4<i>R</i>,5<i>S</i>,6<i>R</i>)-2-[4-Bromo-3-(4-ethoxybenzyl)phenyl]-6-(hydroxymethyl)tetrahydro-2<i>H</i>-pyran-3,4,5-triol)</p>	C ₂₁ H ₂₅ BrO ₆ ; 453.3

Dapagliflozin USP monograph	Ethyl Dapagliflozin	<p>(2<i>S</i>,3<i>R</i>,4<i>R</i>,5<i>S</i>,6<i>R</i>)-2-[4-Chloro-3-(4-ethoxy-3-ethylbenzyl)phenyl]-6-(hydroxymethyl)tetrahydro-2<i>H</i>-pyran-3,4,5-triol.</p>	C ₂₃ H ₂₉ ClO ₆ ; 436.93
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All the above USP monographs known impurities were procured, injected in HPLC-PDA along with the thermal stress sample and found that the degradants observed in the thermal stress sample retention times and UV spectrums match with that of the procured known impurities of Hydroxy Dapagliflozin and Oxo Dapagliflozin (**Figure 2a-2d**). Also, the mass spectra ($M+1$, m/z) of the degradants observed in the thermal stress sample were comparable with the mass spectra ($M+1$, m/z) of these individual known impurities, Hydroxy Dapagliflozin and Oxo Dapagliflozin, thus concluded the structures of the degradants and the identification of the degradants from the thermal stress sample (**Figures 3-4**).

Figure 2a: Overlay of chromatograms of thermal stress sample and individual impurities.

Figure 2b: HPLC-PDA chromatogram and UV spectrum of Hydroxy Dapagliflozin Impurity.

Figure 2c: HPLC-PDA chromatogram and UV spectrum of Oxo Dapagliflozin Impurity.

Figure 2d: HPLC-PDA chromatogram and UV spectrum of Thermal Degradation Sample.

Figure 3: Mass Spectrum of procured Oxo Dapagliflozin impurity provided in COA.

Figure 4: Mass Spectrum of procured Hydroxy Dapagliflozin impurity provided in COA.

4. CONCLUSION

Degradants observed in thermal stress degradation sample were identified as Hydroxy Dapagliflozin and Oxo Dapagliflozin impurities mentioned in Dapagliflozin tablets USP monograph, basis to retention times matching, UV spectrums concordant and same mass values using HPLC-PDA and LC-MS instrumental techniques.

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